

THE REGULATORY LEGISLATIVE SYSTEM OF THE MASS MEDIA IN THE CASE OF UZBEKISTAN AND CHINA

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Abstract. *In the article, the author suggests that the legal framework of mass media should be further improved. In addition, considers the advantages of cooperation in the field of media and the importance of media in solving problems.*

Keywords: *Mass media law, legislation, communications, China, Uzbekistan.*

НОРМАТИВНО ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬНАЯ СИСТЕМА СМИ НА ПРИМЕРЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА И КИТАЯ

Аннотация. *В статье автор предлагает дальнейшее совершенствование правовой базы СМИ. Кроме того, рассматриваются преимущества сотрудничества в сфере СМИ и значение СМИ в решении проблем.*

Ключевые слова: *Закон о СМИ, законодательства, связь, Китай, Узбекистан.*

INTRODUCTION

The People's Republic of China started reforms in its territory in the 1980s. The government aimed to develop the economy in all areas. As it's known, the Media industry has become an integral part of social daily life. The main efforts of the government of the country directed to formation of a new economic system - a socialist market economy. The so-called "Chinese model" implied enhancing economic growth, accompanied by a policy of openness, the country's entry into modern civilization, the strengthening of relations with other countries. These changes, however, have not affected the sphere of mass media regulations, which continues to function under strong control by the state and the Chinese Communist Party. The country still does not have a separate law on the media, although work on its creation has been ongoing since the beginning of the reform period. At the same time, there are not any detached law on the media in Uzbekistan. In both counties you don't see censorship directly but they are here. It may encourage the government to protect the state safe. On the other occasions, journalists are given more freedom of publication.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to improve legislation in the field of freedom of speech, the Information Code of Uzbekistan is being developed. It should become a regulatory document designed to unify existing laws. It is expected that thanks to this code, information protection will be properly carried out, both freedom of speech and information security of the individual, society and the state will be ensured.

According to Article 6 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 5, 2014, access to information on the activities of state authorities and management is restricted if the specified information is classified in accordance with the procedure established by law as information constituting state secrets or other secret protected by law. The list of information related to information on the activities of public authorities and management, access to which is restricted, as well as the procedure for attributing information to such information is established by law. At the same time, according to Article 6 of December 12, 2002, followings can't be

subject to restriction: acts of legislation on the rights and freedoms of citizens, the procedure for their implementation, as well as establishing the legal status of public authorities and management bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, public associations and other non-governmental non-profit organizations; information on environmental, meteorological, demographic, sanitary-epidemiological, emergency situations and other information necessary to ensure the safety of the population, settlements, production facilities and communications; information available in the open collections of information and library institutions, archives, departmental archives and information systems of legal entities operating on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

RESULTS

Modern Chinese Legislation differs from the legislation of the countries of the Romano-Germanic decrees, as it does not include direct laws aimed at regulating the activities of the media. China has a Constitution and a number of relevant decrees, acts, administrative and legal norms that have legislative force to the control its media. Let's consider the main legislative provisions that affect the media industry in China: the constitutional foundations of freedom of speech, access to government information, protection from slander. According to the Constitution of the People's Republic of China, the following constitutional provisions are relevant to the media, which mainly relate to freedom of speech. For example, in Article 35th, Citizens of the People's Republic of China appreciate freedom of speech, press, assembly, association, procession and demonstration. In Article 41st, Citizens of the People's Republic of China have the right to criticize and make suggestions regarding the activities of any government agency. Although there is no direct reference to the media, the PRC Constitution does provide laws for media rights to freedom of expression, publication, coverage, and control. [2. 92-94-pages].

The Regulation on the Disclosure of Government Information states that The Media can access government information. According to this, citizens and organizations have the right to receive government information, as well as the right to make requests for obtaining relevant government information, if necessary, this information in economic activities, for life, in research work and other special needs. The response to the request will be given in 15 days.

Of course, laws not only grant rights to the media, but also define their responsibilities. In view of the peculiarities of media coverage and their unlimited influence, it has become very important to limit their behavior within the framework of the law and expediency, so as not to infringe on the interests of citizens and society.

DISCUSSION

Regulating the system of media law in China is opting for adopting two main principles. First of them, Media legislation will improve journalism in China, as it will confirm the scope of work and powers of the media from a legal point of view, and the activities of the media will be supported by law. The media will be able to influence the government more effectively, point out social shortcomings and fulfill their professional responsibilities. Second, Media legislation will help to develop the international influence of Chinese media to other media corporations. With the enactment of the media law, freedom of the press will increase and the quality and scope of news reporting will improve. Foreign media will be able to receive more effective information through the Chinese media. [169-184-pages]. Now, we should comprehend all data about mass media in Uzbekistan. However, the system of regulation media in Uzbekistan is not

enough strong and there is not any special developed law. According to the Constitution of Republic of Uzbekistan, freedom of speech is guaranteed. All other norms about media must follow the main idea of the Constitution.

CONCLUSION

In the developed countries no one can control the flow of information. They may try to block web-sites, messengers, but people know how to bypass it. In order to improve legislation of freedom of speech, the Information Code of Uzbekistan is being developed. It should adopt regulatory document that unifies existing laws. It is expected that thanks to this code, protecting the information will be properly carried out, both freedom of speech and information security of the individual, society and the state will be guaranteed.

REFERENCES

1. Sh.Mirziyoyev Strategy of New Uzbekistan. 2022. [1. 76-page 418].
2. Azizov R.F. Xitoy Xalq Respublikasida Internet faoliyatining huquqiy jihatlari // Vologda huquq va iqtisodiyot instituti byulleteni: jinoyat, jazo, tuzatish. 2015. [92-94-pages].
3. Ibragimova G. Xitoyning Internetni boshqarish va axborot xavfsizligi sohasidagi strategiyasi // Xavfsizlik indeksi. 2013. [169-184-pages].
4. Axborot xavfsizligini tashkiliy-huquqiy ta'minlash: bakalavriat va magistratura talabalari uchun darslik va amaliy mashg'ulot. Polyakova, A.A. Streltsov. Moskva: Yurait nashriyoti, 2016 yil.
5. Yang Chji, Ten Yuehong. Xitoyda zamonaviy jurnalistika: kechki matbuot, mintaqaviy radio. - Minsk, 2011 yil.